

Galactic Center Newsletter

IAUS405: Traversing the Galactic Center in Space and Time, Brno (<https://gc2026.muni.cz/>)

Vol. XXIX / No. 5

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF: Václav Pavlík — EDITORIAL BOARD: Vladimír Karas, Petra Suková, and Maitrayee Gupta

May 22, 2026

EDITORIAL: PROOFS AND PARADOXES

By VÁCLAV PAVLÍK

There is a comforting illusion shared by mathematicians and scientists alike that with enough care, rigour, and data, we will eventually arrive at a complete description of the system we are studying. In mathematics, this illusion was famously shattered in 1931, when Kurt Gödel [1], a Brno native, born 120 years ago, showed that any sufficiently powerful formal system is necessarily incomplete. There will always be statements we cannot prove from within the system itself.

In science, the notion of a *proof* does not exist. We do not prove, we infer. We accumulate evidence, reduce uncertainties, and falsify alternative explanations until the most robust explanation remains. Even then, our confidence rests on a foundation of assumptions that are rarely stated explicitly: the validity of our laws of physics (such as Newtonian gravity or general relativity in the relevant regime), or the reliability of the instruments we design, build, and calibrate.

These assumptions are not weaknesses of the scientific method. Rather, they define the boundaries within which our conclusions hold. When an observation agrees with expectations, it strengthens both the model and the assumptions beneath it; when it does not, it is often unclear which layer is being tested. Discrepancies may point to new physics, to overlooked complexity, or simply to limitations in our measurements. But the richer and more detailed our models become, the harder it is to disentangle these possibilities. In star cluster modelling, we often refer to such all-encompassing approaches as “kitchen sink” models [2].

This is where the parallel with Gödel becomes instructive. His theorem reminds us that incompleteness is not a flaw in construction, but the price paid by sufficiently expressive systems. In other words, the more a system can describe, the more questions it can pose that it cannot answer internally. The Galactic Center is, by any measure, such a system – each new observable sharpens our picture, but also expands the landscape of open questions.

Gödel himself was deeply interested in physics and cosmology [3]. His solutions of Einstein’s equations allowed closed timelike curves – mathematically consistent, physically unsettling. The lesson is not that such universes exist, but that internal consistency alone does not guarantee physical relevance.

As we gathered this week to discuss the Galactic Center, we did so with the state-of-the-art data, increasingly sophisticated models, and awareness of the system’s complexity. It is neither surprising nor discouraging that some aspects remained unresolved. It is simply where active science lives. Incompleteness in this sense is not an obstacle, but an indication of progress. As this is the last issue of this Newsletter, let me wish you all good luck, resilience, and a lot of fun with your scientific projects. ■

- [1] K. Gödel. *Monatshefte für Mathematik und Physik* **38** (1931), 173–198.
- [2] S. L. W. McMillan. “Star Cluster Simulations Including Stellar Evolution”. *Astrophysical Supercomputing using Particle Simulations*. Ed. by J. Makino and P. Hut. Vol. 208. IAU Symposium. 2003, 131.
- [3] K. Gödel. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **21** (3 1949), 447–450.

Kurt Gödel (middle) and Julian Schwinger (right) receiving the first-ever Einstein Award directly from Albert Einstein (left) at the Princeton Inn in Princeton, New Jersey. (credit: IAS)

OUTLOOK: NEW WINDOWS ON THE GALACTIC CENTER

By PETRA SUKOVÁ

The next decade promises to be unusually rich for Galactic Center astronomy. Rather than one big breakthrough from a single instrument, progress will likely come from a sequence of new facilities, each opening a different window onto the inner Milky Way. Together, they should transform our view of Sagittarius A*, the Galactic bulge, and the energetic environment of the Central Molecular Zone.

The first wave is already near. The Vera C. Rubin Observatory (formerly Large Synoptic Survey Telescope; LSST) has begun issuing scientific alerts, with the full survey expected to start later in 2026. This instrument gives astronomy a powerful new engine for variability and transient discovery. NASA's Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope (or the Roman Observatory, for short) should follow very soon, with launch slated by May 2027. For Galactic Center science, the Roman Observatory is especially exciting because its planned surveys include the Galactic bulge and the Galactic plane, exactly the regions where wide-field infrared capability is so valuable.

At high energies, the most exciting new facility is the Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory (CTAO). It expects first data in 2027, and for the Galactic Center, the southern array is especially important: it is optimized for Galactic targets and for the medium- to high-energy regime. This makes

CTAO one of the key future instruments for mapping TeV emission from the inner Galaxy and for probing particle acceleration near the Galactic Center. Its results could clarify the origin of highest-energy Galactic cosmic rays.

NewAthena, ESA's next flagship X-ray observatory, is currently in the study phase, with mission adoption planned for early 2027 and launch targeted for 2037. It is expected to deliver an order-of-magnitude leap in X-ray sensitivity, survey speed, and high-resolution spectroscopy. All this will make it a major future facility for studying hot gas, compact objects, and energetic transients across the Milky Way. For Galactic Center science in particular, NewAthena should offer a powerful new view of the hot and dynamic environment, while also providing rapid follow-up of transient events.

NASA's Ultraviolet Transient Astronomy Satellite (ULTRASAT), also anticipated in 2027, will add a different but complementary capability by providing rapid UV monitoring of transients. Moreover, one especially nice point for a Brno-based meeting is the Quick Ultraviolet Kilonovae Surveyor (QUVIK), the first Czech space telescope and the first Czech UV mission. Its scientific program is led by the astrophysicists from Masaryk University in Brno, including Norbert Werner and Michal Zajaček, making it a particularly fitting local contribution to the future of space astronomy. QUVIK is designed primarily for ultraviolet observations of kilonovae and other energetic transients. Although dust obscuration prevents it from probing the Galactic Center directly, its observations of nearby low-luminosity galactic nuclei and

nuclear transients may still help us better understand accretion physics in systems analogous to our own.

Radio astronomy will also enter a new phase with the Square Kilometre Array Observatory (SKAO), which has already begun commissioning. The first science-verification data are expected in 2027, and early operations are planned for 2029. For Galactic Center studies, this means a huge step forward in sensitivity to pulsars, magnetized gas, non-thermal emission, and radio transients in the inner Milky Way.

For the most detailed work near Sagittarius A*, however, the strongest expectations are attached to ESO's Extremely Large Telescope (ELT). ESO now plans telescope first light in March 2029 and scientific first light in December 2030, with far sharper imaging and spectroscopy capabilities. If Rubin and Roman Observatories broaden the view, ELT should sharpen it dramatically.

Lastly, ESA's Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA) mission and the ground-based Einstein Telescope (ET) are both expected to begin observations in 2035. With them, our view of the sky will expand the multi-messenger domain towards the low-frequency gravitational-wave window.

Hence, the outlook for Galactic Center astronomy is remarkably bright as all of these new observatories begin operation. Future Galactic Center workshops will almost certainly bring a wealth of new discoveries, and the years ahead promise to deepen our understanding of one of the most fascinating regions in the sky. ■

FROM GALAXIES TO THE GALACTIC NUCLEI AND JETS

By MAITRAYEE GUPTA

At the core of many massive galaxies lies an energetic region called the Active Galactic Nucleus (AGN). Driven by supermassive black holes millions to billions of times the mass of our Sun, these compact areas release immense quantities of radiation, frequently outshining the combined stellar populations of their entire host galaxies across the electromagnetic spectrum.

The profound luminosity of an AGN is not fuelled by thermonuclear fusion, but rather by the gravitational potential energy released by the process of interstellar gas and disrupted material spiralling into the black hole's accretion disk. As this matter approaches the event horizon, extreme gravitational forces compress and heat it into plasma at tens of millions of Kelvin, triggering intense emission of UV and X-ray radiation. The most spectacular manifestations of this process are relativistic jets, i.e. collimated outflows of ionized matter ejected at fractions of the speed of light that extend over millions of light-years into the intergalactic medium.

The mechanism behind the launching and acceleration of these highly directional outflows remains one of the premier investigations in modern high-energy astrophysics. Theoretical frameworks indicate that jet formation is inextricably linked to the rotation of the central black hole and the topology of the surrounding magnetic fields. One of the foundational mechanisms for the extraction and launching of this rotational energy is based on the seminal work of Roger Blandford and Roman Znajek [1].

In the Blandford–Znajek process, an ordered, large-scale magnetic field is dragged inward by the accreting matter and twisted into a tight helical configuration by the frame-

dragging effect of a spinning black hole. This configuration establishes a powerful magnetohydrodynamic engine. The spinning event horizon acts essentially as a conductor rotating in a magnetic field, creating a significant potential difference that accelerates charged particles along the polar rotation axis. This process efficiently channels rotational kinetic energy away from the spacetime metric of the black hole itself, launching the observed relativistic jets into deep space.

Understanding these energetic phenomena, as well as many others like them, requires precise, multi-wavelength observations from Earth and space. Resolving the extreme physics surrounding AGNs and mapping the plasma dynamics that govern the distant universe requires space frameworks that can make such observations. Many research programmes around the world support this effort; in the Czech Republic, one such grant is the Space for Mankind research programme by the Czech Academy of Sciences (AVČR). It aims at fostering collaboration between the scientific community and technical teams in the development and testing of new space research technologies, in particular satellite instruments for astronomical observations. The topics of the programme include the involvement in the major space missions of the European Space Agency (ESA), such as the X-ray observatory *NewAthena* or the gravitational-wave space antenna *LISA*. This

initiative and others like it are crucial to continuing to expand our understanding of the universe.

[1] R. D. Blandford and R. L. Znajek. *MNRAS* **179** (1977), 433–456.

Multi-wavelength image of galaxy Centaurus A; by Hubble (visible), Chandra (X-ray), Spitzer (infrared), and the Very Large Array (radio). Cen A's dusty core is apparent in visible light, but its jets are best viewed in X-ray and radio. (image credit: NASA, CXC, SAO; astrophotography by Rolf Olsen, NASA-JPL, Caltech, NRAO, AUI, NSF, UOH, M. Hardcastle)

OPEN QUESTIONS AND PERSISTING CHALLENGES

By VLADIMÍR KARAS

Thirty-eight (!) years have elapsed since the first IAU Symposium (IAUS 136) was organized by Mark Morris (Los Angeles, CA, 1989). Judging from the conference photograph, that meeting was attended by 102 participants. Among many ground-breaking contributions, the talk by Leonid Ozernoy of Harvard-Smithsonian Center of Astrophysics, titled “Constraints on and alternatives to a massive black hole at the Galactic center”, was published in the Symposium proceedings [1]. Over four decades, numerous hypotheses about Sagittarius A* were tested, some of them rejected, but as Karl Popper’s Theory of Falsification teaches us,

Historical photo of IAU 136 Symposium on Galactic center (credit: Kluwer)

scientific theories can never be proved right. So, where exactly do we stand in 2026?

In his remarkable review presented during IAU 405, Mark Morris reviewed outstanding questions that remain unanswered to date. On his list are:

1. What prior history of the central parsec led to the formation of the young nuclear star cluster?
2. Is there current and ongoing star formation in the hostile environment of the central parsec?
3. What are the observable manifestations of the inevitable outflows generated by the accretion flow onto Sgr A*?
4. How often do stellar collisions take place in the central parsec, and have we already observed the aftermath of such collisions?

5. How can we best investigate the expected presence of a concentration of stellar remnants, and in particular, stellar-mass black holes?

6. Where are the neutron stars?

7. What role do magnetic fields play in the central parsec?

Talks and posters circled around these questions and addressed them from different angles. Naturally, completely new questions have emerged, notably, those connected with the multi-messenger era in which we currently live: cosmic rays, gravitational waves, neutrinos, and dark matter.

Apart from discussing hard science, the participants and the general public of the lively Moravian city of Brno had a lot of fun circling around an impressive model of

the black hole and the image of a polarized signal that has been recorded by the Event Horizon Telescope (see the conference photo in the 4th issue [2]).

Great appreciation goes to the Scientific Organizing Committee, led by Michal Zajaček and Rainer Schödel, the Local Organizing Committee, led by Michal Zajaček, Jiří Dušek and Jan Janík, and to Václav Pavlík, the Editor-in-Chief of the Galactic Center Newsletter, the last issue of which you are reading, and to IAU and the meeting participants for making this event a great success. ■

[1] L. M. Ozernoy. *Symposium - International Astronomical Union* 136 (1989), 555–566.

[2] *Galactic Center Newsletter*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19606199>. 2026.

SUMMARY OF IAU SYMPOSIUM 405 AND THE NEXT GC WORKSHOP

By MICHAL ZAJAČEK

The GC workshop 2026 is coming to an end, and there are already ongoing discussions about the next GC workshop venue. Let us first look back at the GC workshop 2026, which was also the IAU Symposium 405 and the first IAU symposium in Brno.

At the symposium, there were slightly more than 200 registered participants. This is a bit higher than the number of actively contributing researchers (193). The keynote opening talk was delivered by Andrea M. Ghez (UCLA), who received the Nobel Prize in Physics in 2020, which was shared with Reinhard Genzel and Roger Penrose. Each of the six sessions was introduced by a review talk (and Session 1 – Sgr A* and its interaction with the environment – was introduced by two review talks). The review talks (seven in total) were followed by 15 invited talks. There was a larger number of contributed talks (89) that covered all the essential areas (from Sgr A* to the Cen-

tral Molecular Zone), and thanks to them, we indeed managed to traverse the Galactic center in space and time. We have had 81 registered posters that are available in the online gallery at <https://gc2026.muni.cz/programme/posters>.

Following the tradition, at the conference dinner of the IAU 405, the following GC venue was selected, i.e. it was signed on a napkin by Daryl Haggard and Michal Zajaček. It is expected to take place in or around Montreal, Canada, in June 2028, and the main organizer will be Daryl Haggard from McGill University. ■

Official signing of the organization of the following GC workshop venue.